

A STUDY ON EFFICACY OF PANCHATIKTA GHRITA GUGGULU IN THE MANAGEMENT OF DADRU WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TINEA INFECTION

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ABSTRACT

Skin disorders in Ayurveda are included under a broad classification i. e. Kustha. According to Ayurveda Kustha is a Tridoshaja vyadhi. It is broadly classified into Mahakustha and Kshudrakustha. Mahakusthas can be co related with different types of Leprosy and kshudra kusthas can be correlated with different bacterial, fungal, viral, inflammatory and atopic skin disorders. Dadru is one of the Kshudra kusthas which is the result of kapha and pitta dosha dusti. Sign and symptoms of Dadru are Kand, Raga, Pidaka And Mandala. So Dadru can be co related with dermatophytosis or Tinea infection. Tinea infections become chronic if not treated properly. **Aim:** To study the efficacy of Panchatikta ghrita guggul in the management of Dadru. **Materials And Method:** A case study was done on one patient of Dadru or chronic tinea corporis with Panchatikta ghrita gugglu. The drug was given as 2pills (500mg)

twice daily orally for 2 months after food with lukewarm water. During treatment special Ahar and Vihar were advised. Subjective parameters for assessment of improvements were Kand, Raga, Pidaka, Size of mandala and number of Mandala. Objective parameter for assessment was KOH Mount of skin scraping for analysis of fungal elements. **Results:** Improvements were seen in both subjective and objective parameters. All the symptoms were totally cured after the end of the treatment after 2 months.

KEYWORDS: Kustha, Kshudra kustha, Dadru, Dermatophytosis, Panchatikta ghrita guggul., KOH Mount.

INTRODUCTION

According to Ayurveda the disease which makes our body ugly is known as Kustha.^[1] All skin disorders are included under Kustha according to the Ayurveda. When the disease invades twasa only, then the signs and symptoms of Kshudra khustha appears. When the vitiated dosha after infecting twasa goes to the deeper dhatus and cause abnormalities there, then the symptoms of Maha khustha appears. Dadru is one of the Kshudra kusthas.^[2] The sign and symptoms of Dadru are kandu, raga, pidaka, mandala and elevated skin lesion.^[3] Main symptom of Dadru is kandu or itching. We can correlate Dadru with the Superficial fungal disease or Dermatophytosis. Pitta and kapha dosha is involved in Dadru.^[4] Acharya Susrut included Dadru in Mahakusthas.^[5] Susruta mentioned dadru is having spreading nature, tamra varna yukta, itching and pidaka yukta.^[6] So the sign and symptoms reflects the involvement of Pitta and Kapha dosha. Dermatophytosis are a group of fungal infections caused by Dermatophytes.^[7] This infection generally confined to the cornified layer of the skin and its appendages.^[7] A variety of inflammatory and allergic response are seen due to fungal metabolic products. Dermatophytes mainly infect skin, hair and nails and it is popularly known as Tinea Or Ring Worm.^[7] According to Ayurveda the principle of treatment of a disease is to treat the Anubandhya (main) dosha first then after to the Anubandha (Secondary) dosha. So in kustha roga also this theory is applied. In the current study a drug Panchatikta Ghrita Guggulu is selected from Bhaishjyarnavali Kustharogadhikara.^[8] According to Ayurveda Panchatikta ghrita guggulu is having sothahara properties.^[9] The five main ingredients are. Patola, Vyaghri, Guruchi, Vasa And Nimba. All are having tikta rasa. So the aggravated dosha kapha and pitta get subsided easily. Again due to the action of ghrita raga and brana were healed easily. Due to the action of all ingredients the signs and symptoms of allergy and inflammation like itching, redness, elevated patches are decreased.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

- To study Ayurvedic and Modern concept of Dadru.
- To evaluate the efficacy of Panchatikta ghrita guggulu in the management of Dadru.
- To study the mode of action of Panchatikta ghrita guggulu.

CASE SUMMARY

A case of Dadru was taken for the study. The patient had been suffering from Dadru for more than 5 years. She took allopathic medicine as treatment but didn't get relief. The symptoms

disappeared for sometimes and again the patches relapsed. Then she came to Roga Nidan OPD and after giving treatment, her symptoms were completely cured.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Case description

A 32 years old female patient came to the ROG NIDAN OPD of GACH from nearby village of Guwahati having symptoms of DADRU. The patient had undergone Allopathic treatment since last 5 years. But she didn't get relief and symptoms relapsed again and again. After proper examination the case was diagnosed as DADRU or Ring worm infection (Tinea Corporis). The patient was having itchy erythematous, circular patches on both upper extrimities(number of patches are more in right hand), shoulder, face and waist region. The marjin of patches were elevated with papular lesion. The size of patches were different i. e. varried from largest one being 7 sq. cm to smallest one 3 sq. cm. Number of patches were more than 10. No other family members were affected from the same disease. In general examination BP and pulse rate was normal; pallor, icterus and cyanosis were absent. The patient had been suffering from Hypothyroidism since last 2 years and menstrual history was irregular and painful.

Patient's history

- Number of patient- 1
- Age- 34 yr
- Sex- Female
- Type of patient- OPD Patient

Chief Complaints

1. Reddish brown coloured skin lesion present on face, back of neck, upper extrimities, and waist region.
2. Excessive itching.
3. Slight watery discharge after itching.

Baseline Findings

1. Multiple(more than 10 patches) erythematous patches found on face, back of the neck, upper extrimities and waist region.
2. Marjins of patches were elevated and clearly defined.

3. Size of patches were different. Biggest patch was present on the back of neck (size 7Sq cm.)
4. Center of patches were clear..
5. Pidaka (papule) were present at the marjings of the patches.

History of present illness

The patient had been suffering from sign and symptoms like Dadru for more than 5 years. She had undergone Allopathic treatment but did not get relief. Then she came for Ayurvedic treatment. After proper examination and investigation the disease was diagnosed as Dadru or Ring worm (Tinea corporis) and Ayurvedic treatment given to the patient.

INVESTIGATION

KOH mount for skin scraping test for fungal elements.

Personal History

AHAR

Mixed diet

Ahar shakti_Madhyam

Ruchi_Aruchi

Nidra_Prakrit

Mutra_Prabritta

Mala_Vivandha

Vyasana_Betel nut

VIHAR

Kayik_Nis swesta

Vachik_Alpa bhasan

Manasik_Chinta.

Physical Examination

Blood pressure_130/80 mm of Hg

Pulse_84 beat /min

Respiration_18/min

Pallor_Mild

Icterus_Absent

Cyanosis_Absent

Clubbing_Absent

Lymph node_Not palpable

Menstrual history- (2-3 days/ Irregular/Painful) / (22- 25 days)

Co morbidities- Hypothyroidism for 5 yrs (on medication).

Family history- Nothing significant.

DIAGNOSIS

DADRU (TINEA INFECTION)

TREATMENT PLAN

Medicine: Pancha tikta ghrita guggul.

Frequency of medication - 2 pills(500mg) twice daily with lukewarm water after food.

Duration- 2 months

Follow up- At every 15th day

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The results of the treatment was evaluated before and after treatment on the basis of Subjective and Objective parameters.

Subjective parameter. - It includes

1. Kandu (Itching)
2. Raga (Erythema)
3. Pidaka (Papule)
4. Size of mandala(patch).
5. Number of mandala.

Objective parameter. - KOH mount for skin scraping test

Subjective Assessment criteria

Assessment criteria for subjective parameters was based on grading system taken from a publication. Size of patches were measured by using graph paper. In this case multiple lesions were present. So the size of largest lesion was taken into consideration.

1. Kandu - Table 1- Row a. Assessment criteria for Kandu
2. Raga- Table 1- Row b. Assessment criteria for Raga
3. Pidaka- Table 1- Row c. Assessment criteria for Pidaka

4. Size of mandala- Table 1- Row d. Assessment criteria for size of mandala

5. Number of mandala- Table 1- Row e. Assessment criteria for number of mandala

Table 01: Grading of Subjective assessment criteria.

Sign & symptoms	Grading	Score
Kandu (Row a)	• No Itching	0
	• Itching present rarely	1
	• Disturbing patient's attention	2
	• Severe itching disturbing patient's sleep	3
Raga (Row b)	• Normal skin colour	0
	• Faint Red	1
	• Very bright Red	2
Pidaka (Row c)	• Absent	0
	• 1-2 pidaka in one affected part	1
	• 3-4 pidaka in one affected part	2
	• More than 4 pidaka in one affected part	3
Number of mandala (Patch) (Row d)	• No patch	0
	• 1-2 patch	1
	• 3-4 patch	2
	• More than 5 patch	3
Size of mandala (Patch) (Row e)	• Total disappearance of patch	0
	• 1/2 to 2 sq. cm	1
	• 2 -5 sq. cm	2
	• > 5 sq. cm.	3

COMPOSITION OF DRUG

Drug	Latin name
Nimba	Azadirachta indica
Guruchi	Tinospora cordifolia
Vasa	Adhatoda vasaka
Patol	Trichosanthes dioica
Kantakari	Solanum xanthocarpum
Ghrita	Ghee
Guggul	Commiphora mukul

TREATMENT GIVEN

The patient was prescribed Pancha Tikta Ghrita Guggul in a dose of 2 pills(500mg) twice daily with lukewarm water for 3 months. Follow up were done every 15th day. During the treatment the patient was advised to take laghu, ruksha and tikta rasa pradhan diet. Mild exercise and daily bathing was advised. Viruddhahar, divaswapna and vega dharan were prohibited.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Sign and synonyms	1st Follow up (At 15th day)	2nd Follow up (At 30th day)	3rd Follow up (At 45th day)
Kandu	3	1	0
Raga	2	2	1
Pidaka	3	3	2
Size of mandala	3	1	1
Number of mandala	3	2	1

BT & AT COMPARISION

SIGN AND SYMPTOMS	BT SCORE	AT SCORE	RESULT
KANDU	3	0	100% cured
RAGA	2	0	100% cured
PIDAKA	3	0	100% cured
SIZE OF MANDALA	3	0	100% cured
NUMBER OF MANDALA	3	0	100% cured

EFFECT OF THERAPY ON SUBJECTIVE PARRAMETER

After continuing Ayurvedic treatment for 2 months, the patient showed improvement in all the symptoms. Kandu was reduced in 1st follow up and became absent totally in 3rd follow up. Improvement in Raga was slow and became normal at the end of the treatment, Pidaka reduced on 3rd follow up and complely cured at the end of the treatment. Size of patch was decreasing slowly and reduced totally on last follow up. No patch was present at the end of the treatment.

EFECT OF THERAPY ON OBJECTIVE PARAMETER

KOH MOUNT for Fungus element was found positive before starting the treatment. After completion of treatment KOH MOUNT for Fungal elements was repeated and found negative.

PROBABLE MODE ACTION OF PANCHATIKTA GHRITA GUGGULU

Panchatikta Ghrita Guggulu is tikta rasa pradhan aushadhi. The main ingredients of this drug are panchatikta gana dravya, ghee and guggulu. All the panchatikta dravyas are having tikta, laghu and ruksha guna. Ghee subsides pitta and have brana soshak property. It has action on Vikrit kapha, meda and kleda formation. The alkaloid present in Nimba is Nimbidin. It has mainly anti inflammatory and anti ulcer effect. Guruchi acts as an antioxidant and immunomodulator¹⁰. Guggulu has Katu, tikta, kashay and madhur rasa, ushna veerya and katu vipak. Ghrita acts as pitta shamak which helps in varna ropana⁹. All the ingredients present in panchatikta Ghrita guggulu are having dosha prasamana action and helps in

regeneration of Dermatocytes. As a result sign and symptoms like Kandu, Raga, Pidaka and Mandala were reduced totally.

CONCLUSION

From the study the following conclusions may be drawn-

1. Sign and symptoms of Dadru can be correlates with Tinea or Ring worm infection.
2. Kapha and Pitta dosha is involved mainly in Dadru.
3. Tikta rasa pradhan aushadhi can be advised in Dadru.
4. Panchatikta Ghrita Guggulu showed complete improvement in all the symptoms of Dadru.
5. It is also effective in chronic case of Dadru.

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